

UDK: 338.48

THE DIFFERENCES AND CHARACTERISTICS OF YOUNG TRAVELLERS

Akhrorova Nilufar Uktamovna,

Doctoral student of "Silk Road" International University of

Tourism and Cultural Heritage

n.u.axrorova@buxdu.uz

***Abstract:** Youth travel is considered to the future of tourism and hospitality industry, because today's youth are fond of travel as much as, in the future they will also travel and pass on this love of travel to the next generation. This article gives information about what differentiates youth travel from other types of tourism.*

***Keywords:** young people, youth travel, tourism types, travelling features.*

INTRODUCTION

One of the important characteristics of young people is their potential for health: they are the healthiest group in terms of physical and psychological aspects among the population. Young people have a significant reserve of unspent energy, which, with skilful leadership, can revitalize society. Fundamentally, the latest technologies, control systems that make up the main factors of economic intensification can only be created by people of a new, non-traditional type of thinking. As one of the most important social groups, young people are not only included in the structure of social relations, but also transform them, realizing their innovative potential, is an important indicator of existing trends and the general direction of development of the whole society. This is the most mobile part of society, which has an active impact on the dynamics of the social structure, changes in the class.

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON THE TOPIC

Youth as a special social group is studied within the framework of many sciences, such as history, political science, philosophy, psychology, pedagogy, sociology, etc. I.S. Kon gave a fairly complete definition of the social group under consideration: “Youth is a socio-demographic group, distinguished on the basis of a set of age characteristics, characteristics of social status and socio-psychological properties due to both. Youth as a definite phase, stage of the life cycle is biologically universal, but its specific age limits, the associated social status and socio-psychological characteristics are of a socio-historical nature and depend on the social system, culture and the regularities of socialization inherent in a given society”. The concept of “youth” is a well-known category of the social world, but, despite the fact that it is studied within the framework of many disciplines, it does not have an unambiguous interpretation, especially in the question of the age boundaries of this socio-demographic group. The age range is the main component in defining the concept of “youth”.

Most sociologists define the youth age from 16 to 29, inclusively. Young people represent a socially economically active part of the population, that is, the most promising stratum of citizens who want to ensure the maximum realization of their needs, while not always choosing simple ways and means of achieving. A distinctive feature of young people is maximalism, a hypertrophied perception of their capabilities and setting themselves such tasks that imply the achievement of only ideal, perfectionist results.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Tourism plays an important role in shaping the personality of a young individual. With the help of tourism, it is possible to create conditions for the disclosure of the potential of youth, as well as to consolidate socially significant norms and values in the youth sphere, based on tolerance, respect for one's own and other people's history and culture. The sports and recreational component in the modern

society of technologies should help a young person maintain health, not allow them to completely immerse themselves in the electronic information world, by changing the type of activity and introducing active recreation as an integral part of the lifestyle. Classification by demographic is important for tourism, that is, dividing the market into certain groups by age, sex, marital status, family composition and consumers, etc.

Demographic characteristics are relatively easy to measure. In socio-demographic terms, young people are characterized as a group distinguished on the basis of age characteristics and differing from others in their social status, values, interests, norms and needs. Young people tend to form small informal communities based on one or more of the above characteristics.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Education is one of the most important activities of young people. The formation of educational strategies for young people is directly related to the state and development of territories and society as a whole. The education system is the most important external regulator of the formation of educational and professional trajectories of young people.

At present, young people, as a more adaptive social group, have the opportunity to possess sufficient information using Internet resources. Therefore, it is not difficult to obtain information about any product or service, to compare similar products. In this regard, possessing information about the quality of a product, its characteristics, in comparison with other products, a representative of young people purchases a product based on these indicators, in rare cases, paying attention to advertising of a particular product.

According to many researches, it can be concluded that at present most of the funds are spent by young people on such items of expenditure as food, housing, and everyday goods. According to the study, young people spend a third of their budget on entertainment and travel. When choosing a product or service, young

people are guided by such indicators as “price” and “quality of goods”, discounts, promotions and bonuses have a significant impact on the choice. But advertising does not influence the choice of a product or service.

Young people have their own pronounced stereotype of behaviour and a way of setting tourist priorities. The following tourist preferences are typical for young people:

purchase of group or individual tours;

priority of educational, sports, entertainment areas;

a choice of any inexpensive accommodation facilities (hotels, hostels, recreation centers);

the possibility of purchasing tours without meals and with a minimum set of additional services;

the rest time may not coincide with the tourist season. Also, various discounts and bonuses are especially attractive, since most of the young people are trying to save money due to the lack of significant financial opportunities.

Young people are, as a rule, students and people not burdened with family, ready for active travel during their holidays. For many of them, travel becomes an end in itself and a way of life. A feature of the youth tourist movement is also active communication of young people in various social networks, through which not only direct communication and exchange of information takes place, but also contacts are made and communities of interest arise.

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that youth is a special socio-demographic group of the population, located in the age range from 14 or 16 to 30 years old, with a high level of physical and psychological health, capable of active mental activity, characterized by intense mobility, relatively other social groups in society. Such indicators contribute to the rapid adaptation of this social group to new living conditions, which has a positive effect on the development of society.

The value of the functions of cultural and leisure activities for young people: the cognitive function aims to organize and maintain the cognitive activity of young people, to disseminate a variety of knowledge and accumulate the necessary social experience. The desire for knowledge is one of the key characteristics of young people. The task of the cognitive function of tourism is to combine life with cognition, the introduction of cognition into everyday activities as part of the usual set of activities;

familiarization with material and spiritual values contributes to the formation of an altruistic, empathic personality – a person whose activities are aimed not only for the benefit of themselves and their loved ones, but also extend to providing a positive impact on other individuals; the dissemination of cultural values among young people and the development of aesthetic views of the individual;

the realization of the creative potential of the individual makes it possible to find application for all acquired knowledge, skills and abilities in any kind of tourism. In this case, the satisfaction of creative interests and aspirations occurs;

the communicative function implies the organization of communication among young tourists to exchange information about common interests, hobbies, current topics (so-called “trends”) and compare opinions about them, as well as for a casual conversation about routine matters and any pressing events.

The objects of local history excursions are buildings, structures directly related to the life and development of the culture of the region, as well as its terrain and natural objects. An object can also be a settlement as a whole or its individual parts (district, square, street, etc.). Local lore material for city excursions is given by many historically formed names of streets, squares, rivers that keep the memory of heroes and events associated with a given city. It has been proved that local history tourism is an effective means of comprehensive development of the individual in harmony with himself and the world around him, his upbringing, social adaptation, and the establishment in the mind of the skills of forming and

maintaining a healthy lifestyle. The tourist and local history system is constantly being updated, moving forward, the same natural place / attraction after years can acquire a completely different meaning for visitors. Thus, youth local history tourism can be defined as a special type of travel within the country, individual or collective in form, when individuals between the ages of 16 and 29 make temporary trips from their permanent place of residence in order to expand the area of their hobbies, knowledge and views, to form a new one, a clearer and more reliable image of cultures, knowledge of the peculiarities of natural phenomena and memorable sights of various regions of their country, as well as the value-orientational attitudes of other people, including those who lived earlier, in a former time era; stimulating the study of foreign and ancient languages, dialects of the native land, expanding social contacts, combining the development of the mind with the development of the body.

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